

**PATRIOTIC EDUCATION AS A NECESSARY
COMPONENT OF
UPBRINGING ON EVERY LEVEL OF
EDUCATION**

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ABSTRACT. The article is devoted to the problem of patriotism and the ways of developing patriotic feelings in schoolchildren and students, the importance and even urgency of this problem in modern life and the ongoing situation in our country and the whole world.

Patriotic education must become one of the most important branches of modern education as young citizens of the country are supposed to understand their role in the development of the country as it will be their duty and destiny to make the country one of the strongest and developed one not only in Europe but in the world.

It is important to choose right methods and methodology to make our children be proud of their country and their citizenship and understand the necessity of tolerant treatment of each other and careful treatment of history and traditions to be decent descendants of our glorious ancestors as it is vital to keep the memory about our past to be able to see the future.

KEYWORDS: patriotic education and upbringing, culture and traditions, heroic past, ancestors and descendants.

The word «*PATRIOTISM*» has become especially important nowadays as our nation is facing a very difficult period when we all need to prove our love to our motherland. And love to the place where a person was born is something sacred that must be kept in our heart for all our life. That is why patriotic education must become important part of educational process not only in school but university as well and even communicating with parents, relatives and friends should contribute to developing

the feeling of love and pride because as English people say there is no place like home and they are absolutely right.

As it was stated by Inna Naida, Yuliia Rudenko and others «*The current state policy of forming patriotic education for the youth should be used based on highquality tools for popularizing civic positions and respect for the country. This will have a positive impact on the future political life of the country. Positive attitudes of the youth toward their country and active citizenship will contribute to political development and economic growth*» (Naida, 2023, p. 139). Moreover, «*patriotic education involves the formation of respect and love for one's own country. Patriotism is different from nationalism, as it implies its liberal form of manifestation, which is used in everyday life, by spreading the love for the country through active social actions, use of the state language, and legal activities. Patriotism and patriotic education are aimed at forming a single goal, which involves the creation of cultural values in young people, based on respect for the state. The formation of patriotic education is a top priority for any state*» (Naida, 2023, p. 147). That is why it is almost impossible to lessen the importance of patriotic education at school and university as upbringing real patriots we are taking care of the future, our land and our descendants who will keep the memory about our past and keep out culture and traditions.

A lot of famous people have spoken their word about patriotism. We will provide a few quotations to highlight the importance of understanding the real nature of it:

«*Love your country. Your country is the land where your parents sleep, where is spoken that language in which the chosen of your heart, blushing, whispered the first word of love; it is the home that God has given you, that by striving to perfect yourselves therein, you may prepare to ascend to him*» (Giuseppe Mazzini, 1848) (The Quote Garden).

«*Patriotism, or the peculiar relation of an individual to his country, is like the family instinct. In the child it is a blind devotion; in the man an intelligent love*» (George William Curtis, «Patriotism» an oration delivered before the graduating class at Union College, Schenectady, New York, 1857) (The Quote Garden).

If we think about famous Ukrainian poetry about the country or even motherland it is impossible to omit the wonderful verse by Vasyl Symonenko «The Swans of Motherhood» written in 1962 on the territory of Cherkassy region, the land where the greatest Ukrainian poet Taras Shevchenko was born:

*You can surely choose your friends and pick a spouse, my son,
But of choices for a country there is only one.*

*You can pick a friend and a blood-brother too,
But your mother's already chosen for you.*

*Always they're with you, wherever you go —
Your mother's eyes, the home you used to know.*

*And if foreign fields be the resting place for you,
The willows and poplars will come without ado.*

*They will stand over you, and rustling their leaves,
Their baleful farewell will touch your very eaves.*

*For you can choose anything at all, my son,
But of Fatherlands for you there's only one (Symonenko, 2015).*

These words must become grace for every Ukrainian who calls himself or herself the one as Vasyl Symonenko pointed out that we can choose almost anything besides our parents and our motherland. That is why it is vitally important to read and even learn by heart such verses as they must always be in the heart and soul of every true Ukrainian. But to have these words written in our heart the teacher must be especially careful in presenting and discussing the material as such verses are to be felt but not only repeated. They touch every strings of the soul but schoolchildren are supposed to let the poetry enter their hearts. And here comes the important task of the teacher who must show the example.

The same thing can be said about the verse by Volodymyr Sosiura «Love Ukraine» written in 1944, the period when Ukraine was facing one of the most terrible wars taking place on its territory. The fourth part of the population of the country of that time did not survive the war and we must always remember about that loss. At the same time it is very important to make Ukrainian schoolchildren do the following:

*Love your Ukraine, love as you would the sun,
The wind, the grasses and the streams together...
Love her in happy hours, when joys are won,
And love her in her time of stormy weather.*

*Love her in happy dreams and when awake,
Ukraine in spring's white cherry-blossom veil.
Her beauty is eternal for your sake;
Her speech is tender with the nightingale (Andrusyshen, 1963).*

We shouldn't forget that the national symbol of our country Taras Shevchenko ordered us to «Love your Ukraine» as people without love to their motherland are like humans without soul, so they can't feel anything. They can't love each other and without it they are like empty bowls. That is why it is very important for the teachers to show their true love to the country as it is vital to teach schoolchildren the same and it is obvious that without showing an example it is impossible to do it.

It may seem that only schoolchildren could and must be taught to love their motherland but it is not correct. Students are equal citizens of the country so they must be aware that it is important to treat the motherland with love and tenderness as the future of the whole nation depends on it.

As it was stated in the work of Serdar Malkoç and Fatih Öztürk, «*Patriotism is among the important values in civic and social studies education. In other words patriotism both effects and is effected by civic and social studies education. Also type, aim or directions of research on patriotism varies from country to country based on the educational agenda*» (Malkoç, 2021, p. 154). And it means that every country has its own understanding and its own meaning of patriotism. But it goes without saying

that patriotic education must be important and necessary part of educational process on every level starting from the young age. Moreover, the process of patriotic education should be as long as life so it should never be stopped.

There are many ways to show our young generation that love to motherland is important for their survival as people and nation. They are patriotic films with particular plot, patriotic poetry and songs, patriotic art like painting and embroidery. Schoolchildren can and must help older generation to keep our traditions and our history. That is why it is so important to teach them to do it.

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